

Descriptive Statistics of Surveyed Institutions in the EUI

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1. Analysis of respondents

The survey remained opened for 40 days, between January 22nd and March 5th 2024. The population is represented by the 354 Higher education institutions participating in one of the 39 Alliances funded in 2019 and re-funded in 2002 (16 Alliances) and in 2020 re-funded in 2023 (23 Alliances). The population includes the 'associated partners' from Switzerland and UK, therefore the number of 354 is higher than the official number released by the European Commission which only includes those HEIs that are entitled to receive the EU grant (340 HEIs).

The percentage of valid answers is 29,66% of the entire population as represented in table 1

Table 1

Respondents' rate

	<i>n</i>	<i>% on population</i>
Population	354	
Survey received	105	29,66%

The 105 respondents are part of 35 out of 39 Alliances, which are represented in Figure 1 below. Some of the Alliances are more represented (Una Europa, Forthem, Arqus, Eciun) than others. Table 2 illustrates the percentage of respondents per Alliance.

Figure 1

Respondents per Alliance

Table 2*Number of respondents per Alliance and percentage rate per Alliance*

ID	Respondents per Alliance			% Rate per Alliance		
	Name	n	% on total	Name	n HEIs	% per Alliance
1	4EU+	0	0,00%	4EU+	7	0,00%
2	ARQUS II	7	1,97%	ARQUS II	9	77,78%
3	AURORA	4	1,12%	AURORA	9	44,44%
4	CHARM-EIGHT	4	1,12%	CHARM-EIGHT	8	50,00%
5	CIRCLE-U	2	0,56%	CIRCLE-U	9	22,22%
6	CIVICA	4	1,12%	CIVICA	10	40,00%
7	CIVIS	0	0,00%	CIVIS	11	0,00%
8	E3UDRES	0	0,00%	E3UDRES	9	0,00%
9	EC2U	1	0,28%	EC2U	9	11,11%
10	ECIUn+	7	1,97%	ECIUn+	12	58,33%
11	EDUC	3	0,84%	EDUC	8	37,50%
12	EELISA	2	0,56%	EELISA	9	22,22%
13	ENGAGE.EU	4	1,12%	ENGAGE.EU	9	44,44%
14	ENHANCE	4	1,12%	ENHANCE	10	40,00%
15	ENLIGHT	3	0,84%	ENLIGHT	10	30,00%
16	EPICUR-SHAPE-IT	2	0,56%	EPICUR-SHAPE-IT	10	20,00%
17	ERUA	2	0,56%	ERUA	8	25,00%
18	EU-CONEXUS Plus	1	0,28%	EU-CONEXUS Plus	9	11,11%
19	EU-GLOCH	1	0,28%	EU-GLOCH	9	11,11%
20	EUNICE	3	0,84%	EUNICE	10	30,00%
21	EUniWell	2	0,56%	EUniWell	10	20,00%
22	EURECA-PRO	1	0,28%	EURECA-PRO	9	11,11%
23	EuroTeQ	2	0,56%	EuroTeQ	8	25,00%
24	EUT+	3	0,84%	EUT+	9	33,33%
25	EUTOPIA	2	0,56%	EUTOPIA	10	20,00%
26	FILMEU	1	0,28%	FILMEU	8	12,50%
27	FORTHEM	8	2,25%	FORTHEM	9	88,89%
28	INVEST	0	0,00%	INVEST	7	0,00%
29	NEUROTECH EU	4	1,12%	NEUROTECH EU	9	44,44%
30	Run EU	1	0,28%	Run EU	9	11,11%
31	SEA-EU	0	0,00%	SEA-EU	9	0,00%
32	T4EU	2	0,56%	T4EU	10	20,00%
33	ULYSSEUS	2	0,56%	ULYSSEUS	8	25,00%
34	UNA EUROPA	11	3,09%	UNA EUROPA	11	100,00%
35	UNIC	4	1,12%	UNIC	10	40,00%
36	UNITA	3	0,84%	UNITA	10	30,00%
37	UNITE!	2	0,56%	UNITE!	9	22,22%
38	UNIVERSEH	2	0,56%	UNIVERSEH	7	28,57%
39	YUFE	1	0,28%	YUFE	9	11,11%
TOTAL		105	29,49%	TOTAL	356	

In terms of Country representations, the sample covers 23 Countries, out of which 19 are Member States, two are EFTA-EEA Countries (Iceland and Norway) and two are 'Partner Countries' (Switzerland and UK). Eight Member States are not represented (Slovenia, Malta, Cyprus, Bulgaria, Estonia, Luxemburg, Croatia and Greece) and four eligible EFTA-EEA and Acceding Countries are not represented either (Lichtenstein, Turkey, Serbia, and Northern Macedonia). Figure 2 illustrates the number of respondents per Country.

Figure 2
Respondents per Country

1.1 Profile of respondents

Respondents cover mainly administrative positions. 18 academic staff (17%) covering the role of academic coordinators of the Alliance within the institution also responded to the survey (Figure 3). Half of the respondents have been recruited to cover a management role in the Alliance and are full time working in the Alliance's activities, as shown by Figures 4 and 5. Most of the respondents are working in the Alliance since its establishment, as shown by Figure 6.

Figure 3
Positions of respondents

Figure 4

Respondent specifically recruited for the Alliance

Figure 5

Percentage of time dedicated to the Alliance by respondents

Figure 6

Seniority of respondents in the Alliance

2. Internationalisation Strategy

The first session of the Survey was aimed to establish the level of embeddedness of the Alliance in the Higher education Institutions involved. The first group of questions was therefore related to the Internationalisation Strategy and in particular it was asked if the Internationalisation Strategy of the respondent's institution, when present, was directly or indirectly mentioning the Alliance and to which concept is the Alliance associated in the Internationalisation Strategy. Figures 7 and 8 show that the vast majority of respondents indicates that the Alliance is explicitly mentioned in their Institutional Internationalisation Strategy.

Figure 7

Does your Internationalisation strategy explicitly reference the Alliance?

Figure 8

Does your Internationalisation strategy explicitly reference the Alliance?

Respondents were also asked, with a multiple choice available, to indicate to which primary objectives is the Alliance associated in their institutional Internationalisation Strategy.

Figure 9 highlights that "Enhancing the overall quality and innovation of education" is the most selected choice, very aligned with the classical Jane Knight's definition of Internationalisation of Higher Education (Knight, 2003, 2008) followed by mobility (quantitative) and transnational cooperation. Interesting to note that also quality of research is mentioned by 30% of respondents and that among the 'other' comments, concepts connected to a holistic interpretation of Internationalisation (such as Inclusion, multilingualism, service to society) are mentioned, as represented in table 3.

Figure 9

Which of the following objectives is the Alliance primarily associated with in your Internationalisation Strategy?

Table 3

Other connections with the Internationalisation Strategy

ID	Text
017	Boosting the digitalisation process
026	Increase mobility in students with disabilities, students that fear international experiences, people with full time jobs or families that cannot go on a regular 6 months exchange
029	Internationalisation of the institution
060	Increasing the number of joint projects with other universities, alliances and industry partners
065	Fostering the co-creation with society
085	Strengthening research partnership network, making study programmes more internationalised
093	digitalisation, multilingualism, inclusion, interdisciplinarity

3. Governance/Management Structures

3.1 Administrative units

Continuing with the aim to establish to what extent are the Alliances embedded in the institutional structures of the participating HEIs, the survey asked 3 questions to detect how institutions are organised in the management of the Alliances. The first question asked if a dedicated administrative unit has been established for the management of the Alliance. The second question asked if the institution has established specific and thematic task forces and working groups for the implementation of alliance's activities and the last question asked if, in addition to the dedicated administrative units and specific task forces and working groups, other administrative structures have been ad hoc created for the management of the Alliance.

As represented in Figure 10, more than two thirds of the Alliances are managed through a dedicated unit and the vast majority of the institutions has also established specific and thematic task forces to implement the activities.

Figure 10

Presence of structures devoted to the implementation of the Alliance

3.2 Pervasiveness of the Alliance in the institution

In order to understand to what extent is the Alliance spread in the Institution, the survey also asked about the involvement of faculties and research Departments and data shows a high level of pervasiveness of the Alliance in the Institutions. It would be interesting to detect, using variables from ETER Database describing the typology and size of institutions, what is the variation of this answer according to the institutional typology and size (Figure 11).

Figure 11

Faculties and Research Departments involved

In the attempt to observe if the process of involvement of academics in the institutions has been more a top-down or a bottom-up approach, it was also asked how academics have been involved, providing a multiple choice option (Figure 12).

Figure 12

Selection modes for engaging academics into the Alliance

4. Transition from the first to the second phase

Before diving into the Internationalisation practices and the deeper changes in internationalisation, a set of questions was asked to detect the perception of which changes already occurred from the first phase of the alliances, corresponding to the first funding scheme received under the ‘pilot calls’ issued in 2019 and 2020, to the second phase, corresponding to the second funding scheme received in 2022 or 2023. The second funding scheme was larger both in terms of financial resources and in terms of duration (four years). In addition, the second funding scheme required, more than the first one, the consolidation of the Alliance into the institutional fabric.

The questions asked were divided in three sub-sets respectively referring to the ‘Vision’ of the leadership on the purpose and benefits of the Alliance, the clarity of the communication of those benefits to the internal community and the awareness of the peculiarity of the Alliance if compared to other Erasmus projects or to other institutional networks. A final question of this sub-section was aimed at observing whether, in the second phase of the Alliance, the administrative structures were still dictated by the funding schemes structure or if a simpler form of organisation and collaboration was already emerging.

As shown by Figure 13, the vast majority of respondents (48% + 33%) agreed that leadership has a clearer vision of the purposes and added value of the Alliance (see “the Purpose challenge” in Claeys-Kulik et al., 2022) and on the fact that these added values and benefits are now better communicated to the internal community (53% + 22%). The peculiarity of the Alliance when compared to other EU funded projects or other institutional networks of HEIs is also clear (48% + 17%), sign that the ‘identity crisis’ mentioned by many Alliance coordinators in the first phase is probably overcome. However, there is a significant minority (26% + 7%) that doesn’t see any significant transition in the structure of the Alliance towards a simpler form of collaboration and a similar percentage of respondents were undecided on this matter (26%).

Figure 13

Answers related to the ‘vision’ in the transition from the first to the second phase

The second sub-slot of questions was composed by two questions on the commitment of the leadership, both in terms of general commitment and in terms of human resources investment.

Figure 14 shows that a majority of respondents (62% and 69% combined strongly agree and agree) declares that the leadership is more committed and that this commitment is also shown by

an increased investment in human resources for the Alliance (with, however, a significant portion of undecided respondents - 26% and 21% respectively).

Figure 14
Commitment of the Leadership in the second phase

The last sub-set of questions was aimed to identify changes from the first to the second phase in terms of motivation of academic staff and administrative involved in the Alliance, with one question more related to the change in the pervasiveness of the Alliance itself in the institution (eg: growing number of Faculties, research Departments and administrative units involved in the second phase).

Figure 15
Pervasiveness and motivation

Concerning the pervasiveness of the Alliance in the institution, there is alignment of the fact that the phenomenon is expanding into the institutions (89% combined strongly agree and agree). Concerning the motivation of academics and administrative staff, however; despite the majority of respondents declaring that motivations increased, a very important minority of respondents were still undecided (41% and 32%).

5. Internationalisation Practices

The questions asked in this session are mostly related to RQ2: “to what extent the EUI fostered new (innovative, different, more) Internationalisation practices in participating HEIs”. The first set of structured questions explored how the Alliance is affecting mobility of students and staff, both in terms of increase or in terms of the development of new types of mobility.

There is a large consensus (percentages ranging from 70% to 83%) on the quantitative positive impact on the ‘traditional’ physical mobility of students, academics and administrative staff, with the higher percentage of agreement on the increase of administrative staff mobility.

Interesting to note, probably due to the impact of COVID-19, that 83% of respondents either agree or strongly agree on the increase of the blended or virtual mobility of students. Less clear is the response on the same increase of blended or virtual mobility for academic and administrative staff, where the percentage of agreement is more than 60% but with a significant minority of undecided respondents (24% and 25%).

However, the most interesting data is about the “development of new forms of mobility not existing before the Alliance”, where the percentage of agreement is higher than 91% (46% ‘strongly agree’ and 45% ‘agree’). Figure 16 reports all the results of the frequency analysis for the topic ‘Mobility’.

Figure 16

Increased or new Internationalisation practices: Mobility

Completely different are the opinions on the alliance impact on the number of double, multiple or joint degrees, where two tiers of respondents either disagree or are undecided on this kind of impact.

Less demanding collaborative programmes, such as Summer Schools or Short collaborative modules are on the contrary increased thanks to the Alliances for 95% of respondents (Figure 17).

Figure 17

Increased or new Internationalisation practices: Collaborative programmes

Moving from the more ‘traditional’ internationalisation practices to more innovative forms of transnational collaboration in education, Figure 18 shows that the majority of the respondents (and therefore of the institutions in the Alliances) have also increased transnational innovative pedagogies through the involvement of external stakeholders, with percentages of agreement ranging from 43% to 69%. In all the sub-questions there is a significant percentage of undecided respondents.

Figure 18

Increased or new Internationalisation practices: Transnational Innovative pedagogy

The last set of structured questions was introduced to observe how institutions are using a strong internationalisation framework (the Alliance) also to internationalise research. Indeed, the research dimension is embedded in the consolidated definition of Internationalisation of Higher Education. However, the research dimension is usually not included in the Erasmus projects' rationales. Finding a good degree of alignments on the use of the Alliance for the internationalisation of research would therefore add a small contribution to the argument that the Alliances are differentiating from previously funded Erasmus multilateral projects, as well as towards the convergence between the EUI and the IoHE rhetoric.

Despite a significant minority of undecided respondents (ranging from 21% to 26%), the vast majority of respondents, as reported in Figure 19, either agree or strongly agree on the impact of the Alliance on internationalisation of research (in particular on the promotion of multidisciplinary research and transnational trainings for early-stage researchers).

Figure 19

Increased or new Internationalisation practices: Internationalisation of research

6. Spill over and Impact: Towards more deep and pervasive changes?

The last session of the survey has been built to initially detect if second-order changes in internationalisation already occurred in the institutions and if essential enablers of internationalisation have been developed through the participation in the Alliance. Three sub-sections have been created to enquire about Internationalisation mindset.

Figure 20 shows a high degree of alignment on the capacity of the Alliance to foster Internationalisation among the leadership and among the academic and administrative staff, also through the creation of incentives to engage in internationalisation. Respondents are more divided on the capacity of the Alliance in fostering the creation of tools and indicators to monitor of Internationalisation.

Figure 20

Internationalisation “mindset”

The capacity of the Alliance to promote cross-collaboration among departments and administrative units, confirmed by 92% of respondents, is a sign of the pervasiveness of the Alliance and of its capacity to push internationalisation out of the international offices’ enclaves.

A specific answer on the re-use and upscale of educational outputs was aimed to confirm the difference between the Alliance and more traditional Erasmus+ multilateral projects. Also in this case the vast majority confirms this trend, with a larger portion of undecided respondents, as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 20
Institutional “Spill-over”

The last sub-set of questions in this session, represented by Figure 22, is the most important one to highlight the influence of the institutional participation in the Alliances on the implementation of holistic, durable and spread internationalisation activities. Questions of this sub-section include (1) the institutional activities aimed to include elements of internationalisation into policies and programmes (eg: on Diversity and Inclusion or on Sustainable Development); (2) the development of international training programmes for administrative and academic staff and (3) the development of new procedures and internal regulations to favour transnational internationalisation activities. Figure 22 well identifies the degree of alignment of respondents on these dimensions. The degree of agreement ranges from 60% to 82%, even if with still significant minorities of undecided respondents (ranging from 12% to 29%).

Figure 22

Increased capacities and new opportunities

